

THE ROLE OF SUBBASAL NERVE PLEXUS IN THE PATHOGENESIS OF NEUROPATHIC EYE PAIN AFTER KERATOREFRACTIVE SURGERY

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Relevance. Refractive surgery (in particular, LASIK) is widely used to correct ametropia and usually gives good visual results. However, some patients develop chronic dry eye syndrome (DES), which in some cases is accompanied by severe eye pain unrelated to the severity of clinical signs. Current data indicate the development of neuropathic eye pain (NEP) in such patients, associated with damage to the corneal nerves and central sensitization. Diagnosis and treatment of NEP require a specific approach, but in routine ophthalmological practice this pathology often remains underestimated.

Objective of the study. Comprehensive assessment of clinical, sensory and morphological signs of neuropathic eye pain in patients with chronic dry eye syndrome after LASIK surgery.

Materials and methods. From September 2024 to May 2025, a prospective clinical study is being conducted at the Ziyobahsh Multidisciplinary Private Clinic, which currently includes 35 people (70 eyes). Patients are divided into three groups. Group I - 10 patients with a high degree of myopia and symptoms of dry eye syndrome (DES), Group II - 10 patients with a high degree of myopia combined with DES and signs of neuropathic eye pain and a control group - 15 practically healthy volunteers without ophthalmological complaints. The average age of the subjects was 29.3 ± 5.2 years (range from 21 to 40 years). Gender ratio: 20 women (57.1%) and 15 men (42.9%). All participants underwent a comprehensive ophthalmological examination and in vivo confocal microscopy.

Results. The study included 35 people (70 eyes), divided into three groups. The average age was 29.3 ± 5.2 years, women - 57.1%, men - 42.9%. All patients in the main groups underwent LASIK and had a high degree of myopia (≥ 6.0 D). Patients in group I (painless dry eye syndrome) had moderate complaints of dryness (OSDI - 42.5 ± 6.3), decreased tear production (Schirmer test - 6.2 ± 2.1 mm) and TBUT (5.1 ± 1.4 sec). Confocal microscopy showed preserved density of subbasal nerve fibers (1255 ± 115 waves/ mm^2), microneuromas and dendritic cells were not detected. In group II (DES+neuropathic pain), along with dryness (OSDI - 46.8 ± 5.7), severe complaints of pain were observed. The test with

anesthetic was positive in 8 out of 10 patients. According to confocal microscopy, a decrease in the density of nerve fibers (985 ± 130 waves/ mm^2), the presence of microneuromas (in 70% of cases) and an increase in the number of dendritic cells were revealed. In participants of the control group ($n=15$), the density of nerve fibers was 1340 ± 105 waves/ mm^2 , pathological changes were not detected. The obtained data confirm the presence of morphological signs of neuropathy in patients with a pain component after LASIK and emphasize the diagnostic value of in vivo confocal microscopy.

Conclusions. Patients with neuropathic ocular pain after LASIK have characteristic morphological changes in the subbasal corneal nerve plexus: decreased nerve fiber density, the presence of microneuromas, and an increase in the number of dendritic cells. The topical anesthetic test in combination with in vivo confocal microscopy is an effective tool for the early diagnosis of neuropathic pain, allowing it to be differentiated from classic dry eye syndrome.

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